

Citizen Science to characterize Household Hazardous Waste

Collaborative process protocol – Methodology/script of face-to-face and online agoras

This document is intended as a support tool. You are welcome to adapt the ideas and suggestions to your local context. Inside, you will find guidance and complete materials list and a step-by-step script for the day of the agoras.

1ST AGORA – IN PERSON		
Time	Description of the task	Material/Organization
5 minutes	Participants Registration Note: it is very important to invite all the stakeholders directly involved in the action's implementation for this Agora Depending on the size, above 10 participants, there is the need to have make groups to conduct the collaborative process.	✓ List of registered participants ✓ Badges for participants and for the team (if they are above 10) ✓ Pens
5 minutes	Welcome remarks: Briefly thanks to participants their presence and explain how the session will be developed: - Evaluation of characterization process (citizen science) - Propose of measures to improve HHW management - Voting online for the most important measures (next session)	✓ PPT (computer)
10 minutes	Presentation of characterization citizen scientists: The organization will present the main results from the CS HHW characterization in terms of waste amounts and recycling behavior	✓ PPT (computer)
25 minutes	Proposal of measures to improve HHW management: - Start with recycling, then Selective collection, Reuse and Prevent / Reduction Elaborate a table for each option, and with post-its, people will propose measures for each one of the waste management options	✓ Table in PPT (computer), divided in 4 columns. Each column is for each HHW management option. ✓ Post-its ✓ Pens
10 minutes	Validation by the group. The existing table will be validated by the group, to ensure that everyone agrees. This way, it can go further to the next agora.	✓ Previous table ✓ Post-its ✓ Pens

5 minutes	Closing remarks. Thanks to participants their participation and contributions and announce that they need to vote in the second agora.	
PREPARATION BETWEEN AGORAS		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structure of HHW management options by each step of 3Rs – reduce (prevention), reuse, recycle - Elaboration of options at SLIDO platform or mentimeter or similar - Invite people present in the 1st agora 		
2ND AGORA – ONLINE		
Time	Description of the task	Material/Organization
5 minutes	Online participants registration, to confirm their presence.	Internet, computer
5 minutes	Welcome remarks: Briefly thanks to participants their presence and explain how the session will be developed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentation of HHW management options for each option – Recycle, separate collection, reuse and reduction/prevention - for each one, they must select the 2 most important for them - after voting, the results will be presented. 	Smartphones are needed, as well internet connection to vote. PPT (computer)
10 minutes	Voting session. During voting, the results will not be presented, only at the end.	PPT (computer)
10 minutes	Presentation of the results and close of voting. Thanks to participants their participation and contributions. Explain that the HHW management plan will be available online and will be delivered to the municipality.	PPT (computer)

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Prepared by: Ana Pires, João Caseiro, Cátia guarda

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